

Towards the use of Unbundle Smart Meter for Advanced Inverters Integration

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Abstract—The Smart Grid (SG) implementation requires a constant monitoring and control of the power network. An Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) allows the Distribution System Operator (DSO) to know what is happening on the power network. However, existing smart meters are not prepared for an emerging energy market nor to be integrated with LV/MV dispatch centres. The Unbundle Smart Meter (USM) concept allows the integration of existing smart meters in the SG, decreasing deployment costs. This paper presents the USM approach for power inverters management. The USM acts as a residential gateway, enabling the control of energy home devices using an IP-based secure communication network. The USM hosts the necessary services and drivers to provide the end-user with the capability to answer Demand Response (DR) requests from the DSO.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Smart Grid (SG) concept is being implemented on the power network, in order to cope with the increasing demands of Distributed Energy Resources (DER), supported by an information and communication technology (ICT) communication layer [1]. Smart meters have an important role in the SG to enable the monitoring of the whole power network [2], [3].

The electricity market liberalisation increases the need of smart meter deployment [4], [5], increasing also the concerns regarding the end-user privacy and data protection [6].

The Unbundle Smart Meter (USM) concept emerged as a unifying approach of both smart meters and SG architectures [7]. It enables power quality monitoring by providing real-time data [8], [9]. Moreover, it automates remote grid acceptance of large Photovoltaic (PV) deployments [10].

Due to the wide PV power incorporation on the SG, new inverters named smart or advanced inverters are being developed [11]. The main advantage of the advanced inverters is to prevent PV systems from going offline when there is no need [12]. With this, the grid is more stable by preventing voltage and frequency drop. Advanced inverters are also being used for improving distribution feed performance [13], in industry applications [14], and for PV integration [15].

The considered advanced inverter functions are: ramp-rate control, fixed power factor control, Volt/Watt control, Watt-triggered power factor control, Watt-priority Volt/Var control, and Var-priority Volt/Var control [16], [17].

Coordinated control of advanced inverters can provide more optimal solutions than local reactive power control, but a reliable and fast communication infrastructure is required [18]. An efficient DER management demands several communication functionalities, namely: autonomous DER response to local conditions, Distribution System Operator (DSO) direct interactions with DERs, utility broadcast/multicast, aggregator-based interactions, and distributed control approaches [19]. However, these advanced inverter communications bring cyber security issues [20], [21].

This paper presents the Nobel Grid project [22] approach for connecting power inverters. This approach will be demonstrated in two pilot sites: an eco-village in Meltemi (Greece), and in an office building in Brussels (Belgium). The remainder of this paper is as follows. Section II describes the Nobel Grid approach regarding the USM connection to the power inverter, which is described in section III. Section IV presents the test case scenario. Lastly, section V enumerates the main findings and future work.

II. THE NOBEL GRID APPROACH

The Nobel Grid project will provide advanced tools and ICT services to all actors in the SG and retail electricity market in order to ensure benefits from cheaper prices, more secure and stable grids, and clean electricity. These tools and services will enable active consumers' involvement, new business models for new actors, and the integration of distributed renewable energy production. Moreover, it will offer advanced services, not only for DSOs but to all actors in the distribution grid, to improve EU citizens' quality of life [22]. The following impacts are expected:

- Efficient and fair sharing of the electricity distribution benefits to all actors.
- Active participation of prosumers and new players in energy markets, such as aggregators and Energy Service Companies (ESCOs).
- Promoting the implementation of new policies, market rules and legislation for SG and smart metering infrastructure.

- Notable improvement of EU citizens' quality of life by enhancing the European energy mix, reducing Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions.
- Opening new markets for advanced SG and smart metering technologies to foster European industries competitiveness.

Nobel Grid combines three central components operated by unbundled market actors (Fig. 1):

- Grid management and maintenance master framework (G3M),
- Energy Monitoring and Analysis (EMA) app, and
- Demand Response Flexible Market (DRFM) cockpit.

Fig. 1. The connection of Nobel Grid actors.

On the control centre side, there are the G3M and the DRFM components. The G3M framework allows DSOs to control and manage the distribution network, including DER. The DRFM cockpit bridges demand side and DER flexibility with the distribution grid actors to provide services to the DSO, which support network stability and security. The customer side has the EMA app and the USM. EMA app provides prosumers with a mobile and web tool to analyse data concerning electricity consumption and production in real-time. The USM is composed by a classical Smart Metrology Meter (SMM) and by the Smart Meter eXtension (SMX). The USM architecture is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. USM architecture [7].

The SMX acts a customer gateway, communicating with the control centre using a secure communication network. In

this paper, for simplification purposes, it is considered that the USM receives commands from the control centre, regardless if the command was issued by the G3M or the DRFM.

III. PV INVERTER

PV inverters are power electronic devices that are used as interface for PV panels. In the case of PV energy two types of systems can be considered: grid-connected system and off-grid installation. In the first case, there are several possible typologies according to the inverter configuration (central, string or module), to the number of energy conversion stages and to the existence of transformer: transformer-based (at the high or at the low frequency side) or transformer-less.

A. Management functionalities

Originally, the PV inverters were intended to provide active power to the grid. National regulations typically required them to automatically disconnect (and reconnect) from the latter in cases of relevant under/over voltages or frequencies. However, as PV penetration increases, namely at residential or small commercial level, it has been realized that inverters can contribute to grid stability using intelligent control strategies assisted by powerful communications abilities. Besides its common task of automatic disconnection/reconnection under voltage and/or frequency disturbances, the PV inverter will be able to support grid stability using several functionalities, intended to compensate previously mentioned disturbances. These performance functionalities are related with storage availability and are further described:

- 1) *Assisting voltage control at local level:* by absorbing or injecting reactive power, the PV inverter can contribute to voltage control, even if the X/R ratio is relatively low in low voltage grids. The flow of reactive power (from or to the inverter) is controlled by the displacement angle between (grid) voltage and (PV) current, or, equivalently the power factor of the device. The amount of active power injected in the grid (which increases voltage at that node) is controlled simultaneously with reactive power, and its curtailed if required.
- 2) *Implementing voltage ride through operation:* under periods of voltage dips (due to faults in the grid), the PV inverters are required to remain connected without generating over-currents as disconnection could cause cascading of other plants. Under these occurrences, the PV inverter increases its reactive power (if available or stored) in order to recover locally the voltage level.
- 3) *Contributing to frequency control:* grid frequency is determined by active power balance (generation vs. consumption). By increasing or curtailing its production, the PV inverters will assist frequency control avoiding their disconnection in events of under/over frequencies (frequency sensitive operation mode).
- 4) *Compensating grid unbalances:* besides its role in assisting grid stability, the PV inverter is also able to address other issues when considering dispersed generation, namely the unbalance that arises due to in-

creased penetration of single phase sources. These were typically not considered when designing low voltage grids and may not be addressed by conventional means as regulating tap change transformers in substations. Negative consequences of unbalances are e.g. neutral over-currents, voltage asymmetries or increased losses. Grid unbalances will be compensated by PV inverter through an adequate management of transferred power, which is independently injected in each phase. This approach is represented in Fig. 4, where a four-wire device is required for this purpose.

Fig. 3. Connection of the three-phase four-leg PV inverter, intended to compensate grid unbalances.

B. SMX Interface

The PV inverter interfaces with the SMX (part of the USM) using two boards: *communication board* and *control board*. These boards are under development to be fully adapted to Nobel Grid project requirements. The *control board* is responsible for the inverter's operation. The *communication board* is responsible for the communication with the SMX and some high-level functions more computational demanding. The SMX will only interact with the communication board (through Modbus over TCP/IP) as show in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Interaction between the SMX and the PV inverter.

The Modbus interface will be implemented using the Jamod library [23]. The driver in the SMX will be prepared to be as plug-and-play as possible, to allow the connection with other Modbus connected inverters. Since each inverter has its only specific Modbus registers, a configuration file specifying these registers should be provided to facilitate the inverter's integration and interoperability. The Modbus driver in the

SMX reads the file and knows which registers to read/write in order to interact with the inverter.

IV. TEST CASE SCENARIO

The previous mentioned interfaces and devices will be tested in the UNINOVA's micro grid's laboratory at the Department of Electrical Engineering (Faculty of Sciences and Technology/NOVA University of Lisbon). This micro grid laboratory (presented in Fig. 5) comprises a weather station, an occupational monitoring system, energy consumption equipment (standard meters, standard smart meters and USM), energy production equipment (PV panels, wind turbine and hydrogen fuel cell) and energy storage equipment.

The PV power interface will be controlled to support the grid regarding unbalancing currents. If the load current grid is unbalanced, then the amplitude of the AC currents of the PV system will also be unbalanced. The reference of the amplitude of the PV AC currents is defined to compensate the unbalance of the load grid. In case there is more available power on the PV side (the power injected by the PV system is bigger than the load), the PV inverter interface can supply the grid.

To communicate with the PV power interface, several functions were defined to measure values and to define set points. These functions are received in the inverter driver and translated to Modbus commands, which are transmitted through TCP/IP. At the moment, the planned measure functions to be implemented are:

- GetActivePower()
- GetReactivePower()
- GetActivePowerPhase(phase)
- GetReactivePowerPhase(phase)
- GetSoC()
- GetBatteryVoltage()
- GetBatteryCurrent()

The control function to be implemented are:

- SetActivePower(new_value)
- SetReactivePower(new_value)
- SetActivePowerPhase(phase, new_value)
- SetReactivePowerPhase(phase, new_value)
- SetOperationMode(mode)
- SetConstraintOperation(new_value)

The input parameters are *new_value*, *phase*, and *mode*. The *new_value* and *phase* parameters are self-explanatory. The *mode* parameter defines the operation *mode* of the inverter: constrained, normal, battery or grid.

V. CONCLUSION

The SG concept requires an interconnection between all the actors of the energy grid. The ubiquitous presence of the USM allows the end-user to have an active role in the SG. Moreover, the USM provides services and high-level functionalities to the DSO, enabling the end-user DER usage.

This paper shows how the PV inverter can be an asset to the DSO, by combining both production and storage it acts as a hybrid resource where storage can be used for both storing

Fig. 5. Overview of UNINOVA/FCT-UNL's micro-grid laboratory setup.

unused PV energy and also surplus energy from the network. Advanced grid services are enabled through the connection USM-PV inverter.

As future work, the inverter's services will be implemented in the SMX driver and tests regarding communication times will be executed. Moreover, the PV inverter will be deployed in the Meltemi eco-village (Greece), and in Brussels (Belgium) for integration and real-world tests.

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